

A ROBUST DIGITAL WATERMARK PROCEDURE FOR STILL IMAGES USING DCT PHASE MODULATION

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ABSTRACT

A digital watermark is a short sequence of information containing an owner identity or copyright information embedded in a way that is difficult to erase. We present a new oblivious digital watermarking method for copyright protection of still images. The technique is based on modifying the sign of a subset of low frequency DCT magnitude coefficients. The embedding process is adaptive and maintains a compromise between robustness and imperceptibility. A major advantage of the technique is its complete suppression of the noise due to the host image. The robustness of the technique to a number of standard image processing attacks is demonstrated using the criteria of the latest StirMark benchmark test.

1 Introduction

The rapid evolution in multimedia storage and transmission technology such as the internet allows us to store and transmit a large amount of information in a digital format. Since digital data can easily be copied and reproduced in a way that is perceptually identical to the original, the chance of theft and piracy of intellectual property is increased. Because of this difficulty, owners of multimedia data are often reluctant to allow their creations to be distributed. Digital watermarking represents a good solution to the above problem, since it makes it possible to identify the source, author, creator, owner, distributor, or authorized consumer of the data source. There are several requirements a good digital watermark must satisfy [1]. These requirements include perceptual invisibility, robustness and tamper resistance, high bit rate, security, and unambiguity. In recent years, the area of digital watermarking has gotten considerable attention from researchers, and numerous techniques have been proposed. Unfortunately, most of these techniques do not share a common means of comparison, especially in the area of robustness. Several techniques claim to be robust but only against certain types of attacks such as compression or filtering. In many techniques the inventors do not test other attacks such as geometric attacks, which are particularly diffi-

cult to survive [2]. There are a variety of techniques that exist in the image digital watermarking literature. For an overview of these techniques one can refer to [3, 1, 4, 5]

2 Proposed Watermarking Technique

In this section, we describe a new watermarking technique for copyright protection of digital images. The technique operates in the DCT domain by embedding a sequence of 100 bits onto a subset of DCT coefficients. The selected coefficients are low frequency coefficients, with mid to high range magnitude values. The basic principle of our watermarking technique is to set the phase of a group of selected coefficients in accordance with the embedded bits. It is known that much of the information that characterizes an image is contained in its phase [6]. This statement is true whether the transform is real or complex. This implies that the phase must be quite robust to image processing operations that preserve the integrity of the image.

Let $x(n_1, n_2)$ be some image of size $M \times N$, and let the corresponding DCT signal be $X(K_1, K_2)$. The transform is divided into two subsets. The first subset $\mathcal{E}_1 \in \mathcal{R}^L$ embeds the hidden information in it, while the other subset $\mathcal{E}_2 \in \mathcal{R}^{MN-L}$ remains unchanged. The subset selection process is done adaptively [7]. Higher magnitude DCT coefficients are more immune to image processing operations than low magnitude coefficients [8]. Hence, these coefficients are more likely to preserve their phase information when an image has undergone some processing operations. Furthermore, these coefficients preserve the image integrity and its perceptual quality. Coefficients selection is therefore done by first fixing a level of distortion γ , such that the distortion introduced by the embedding process will not exceed that level. Then to maximize robustness, we select the coefficients with the largest magnitude, while keeping the distortion level up to γ . The distortion level can be selected using a pixel-based difference distortion metric, such as the peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR), the absolute difference between the original and the watermarked image or by using some perceptual metric as

suggested in [9].

Our embedding subspace is $\mathcal{E}_1 \in \mathcal{R}^L$, in which we used a private key to randomly select a set of coefficients to embed the hidden information. In our design, we followed the rules suggested in [9], i.e., we embedded 100 bits. Therefore, we use the private key to randomly select a group of 100 coefficients. Next, we represent these coefficients in terms of their magnitude and phase. We can consider positive coefficients as having phase angle $\theta = 0$, and negative coefficients having an angle $\theta = \pi$. Let $|X_i|$ be the magnitude of an arbitrary selected coefficient $\in \mathcal{R}^L$. Its phase θ_i is set as follows

$$\tilde{\theta}_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{to represent binary "1"} \\ \pi & \text{to represent binary "0"} \end{cases}$$

The new coefficient is

$$\tilde{X}_i = |X_i|e^{j\tilde{\theta}_i}. \quad (1)$$

The modified coefficients are expressed in rectangular coordinates and combined with the other coefficients. This embedding technique is similar to baseband binary phase modulation, in which the coefficient phase represents the binary transmitted data and the coefficient magnitude represents the carrier amplitude. After combining all the coefficients, we take the inverse DCT to obtain the watermarked image $\tilde{x}(n_1, n_2)$.

The watermark extraction process is relatively simple in the absence of geometric transformations. We simply select the coefficients using the same private key we used previously and extract their sign information. The binary watermark is decoded from the sign information by using the encoding rule in reverse. One of the main advantages of this technique is the cancellation of the noise due to the host image, since the magnitude of the host image does not effect the phase during the decoding process. This means the only noise that needs to be taken into consideration is the noise caused by processing operations. This, in essence, simplifies our decoding process.

The decoding process in the presence of geometric attacks is more involved. Most transform domain data hiding techniques are ineffective against presentation attacks [2, 10], e.g., geometric attacks. In general, presentation attacks do not destroy the watermark, but rather disrupt the coefficient's synchronization. In many of these attacks, it is possible to recover the watermark if the original image is available during the extraction process. Since the technique presented is oblivious, we use an iterative searching technique to cope with geometric attacks. The searching technique seeks to emulate the inverse operation of the attack. For example, if an image is rotated by an angle θ , the owner knows that the image has been rotated, but does not know the exact angle of rotation. The iterative searching algorithm rotates the image by very small amounts in the opposite direction until we reach a position where the bit error

rate drops dramatically, or when computing the correlation with the original watermark, a high correlation is obtained. Note that the iterative searching approach becomes more computationally expensive when the geometric attack does not introduce visible changes in the watermarked image. For example, for small shearing attacks or minor affine transformations, it is not clear what inverse operations need to be performed, and many inverse operations have to be tried first before a match is found. In the case of random bending, the computation is too lengthy and expensive and we often declare the watermark is not detected. If the original watermarked image is available, then the recovery of the watermark is easily obtained by comparing the available image with the original one and applying the inverse operation of the attack.

Two variations of our technique were examined to illustrate the idea of this technique. One selects coefficients from the global DCT of the host image, while the other divides the image into blocks and selects one DCT coefficient from each block. Figure 1-a shows the original image and Figure 1-b shows the watermarked image using the global DCT approach.

(a) Original Lenna image.

(b) Watermarked image.

3 Test Of Robustness

To compare the new technique with other existing techniques [11], we followed the guidelines suggested in [9]. We used a 512×512 gray level image, with 100 embedded bits. To examine the robustness of the technique, we used the latest StirMark benchmark tests and measured the bit error rate (BER). To assess the distortion level γ , we used quantitative measures. In particular, for the global case we set the watermark strength so that the maximum absolute difference between the original and watermarked image did not exceed the value 6, i.e.,

$$|x(n_1, n_2) - \tilde{x}(n_1, n_2)| \leq 6 \quad \forall n_1, n_2 \quad (2)$$

which corresponds to a peak signal-to-noise distortion (PSNR) of about 45 dB. This results in a watermarked image which is almost identical to the original image under normal viewing conditions. For the block DCT approach, we only watermarked the central part of the image, which was done to avoid losing the watermark when

the image was cropped. The embedding was also done adaptively to avoid any block artifacts which might arise in the embedding process. For the subblock approach we did not consider the absolute difference between the original and watermarked image as a measure. This is because in highly textured areas we can increase the watermark strength, which increases the absolute difference without changing the perceptual quality. However, we used the PSNR as a measure in addition to the perceptual measure to assess the quality of the watermarked image. For the subblock approach the average PSNR value was about 43.5 db. With both variations, the technique demonstrates strong robustness to most StirMark benchmark attacks. The results of the tests are presented both as plots of the bit error rate versus the degree of a few selected types of distortion, and in Table 1, which gives the bit error rate versus a larger variety of distortions. In our simulation, we used the popular image LENA. The StirMark output is usually given in two different formats: a PGM format and a JPEG format. We present the JPEG version here since it represents a worse case scenario.

Most of the errors are due to the cropping operation that is applied either directly or after rotation. One can mitigate this problem by inserting the watermark into the central part of the image either as one large central block or as subblocks. In fact, this is the approach we used for the subblock embedding, i.e., we selected the 320×320 central part of the image and broke it up into 100 blocks of size 32×32 to embed the watermark. In each block, we altered the phase angle of a single coefficients, i.e., we embedded one bit of information. The results indicate the subblock approach performs better than the global DCT approach for some tests such as JPEG compression. This is because the watermark strength can be increased in blocks with high texture without changing the perceptual quality. Furthermore, when the watermark is embedded in the central part, attacks that involve cropping, does not remove the watermark unless the cropping size is big. On the other hand The global DCT approach gives better results for test such as average filtering, and some geometric attacks. One of the drawbacks of this technique is that it is not suitable for multiple embedding since it is not possible to modify the sign of an already modulated coefficient. It can however be used for fingerprinting applications in which every image has one unique label.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented a new oblivious digital watermarking technique based on modifying the signs of a randomly selected group of high to mid range DCT magnitude coefficients. The technique presented has the advantage of suppressing the noise due the host image. Hence, only image processing noise affect the watermark. The embedding process is implemented in

(a) Bit error rate versus degree of JPEG compression.

(b) Bit error rate versus percentage amount of cropping of the whole image area.

(a) Bit error rate versus rotation.

(b) Bit error rate versus rotation and scaling the image to the original size.

an adaptive way to maintain imperceptibility while trying to maximize robustness. We have used the latest StirMark benchmark test as our criterion for examining the robustness of the watermark. Two approaches were used to implement the technique, one using global DCT, the other uses block DCT. The test results indicate that both approaches give impressive results. Recovery of the watermark under geometrical attacks is obtained by a searching method which realigns transform coefficients into their proper locations. We are currently testing this embedding scheme and its robustness to other image transforms. Future work will concentrate on improving the searching technique that synchronizes the selected coefficients and on improving the over all robustness, in particular to attacks such as random bending.

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Table 1: Bit error rate percentage for selected StirMark tests.

Robustness Test	BER for Global DCT	BER for Block DCT
17-row-5-col-remove	0	2
1-row-1-col-remove	0	0
1-row-5-col-remove	0	1
5-row-17-col-remove	0	1
5-row-1-col-remove	0	1
Gaussian-filtering-3-3	0	0
Sharpening-3-3	0	0
scale-2.00	0	0
scale-1.50	0	0
scale-1.10	1	3
scale-0.90	0	0
scale-0.75	0	0
scale-0.50	5	4
ratio-x-0.80-y-1.00	1	2
ratio-x-0.90-y-1.00	0	0
ratio-x-1.00-y-0.80	0	2
ratio-x-1.00-y-0.90	0	0
ratio-x-1.00-y-1.10	0	2
ratio-x-1.00-y-1.20	0	2
ratio-x-1.10-y-1.00	1	1
ratio-x-1.20-y-1.00	1	1
median filtering-2x2	1	1
median filtering-3x3	0	2
median filtering-4x4	3	2
median filtering-5x5	4	3
average filtering-2x2	0	0
average filtering-3x3	0	2
average filtering-4x4	1	8
average filtering-5x5	5	11
StirMark-random-bend	49	51
shearing-x-0.00-y-1.00	2	3
shearing-x-0.00-y-5.00	3	5
shearing-x-1.00-y-0.00	3	3
shearing-x-1.00-y-1.00	2	3
shearing-x-5.00-y-0.00	3	3
shearing-x-5.00-y-5.00	5	4
linear-1.007-.010-.010-1.012	3	2
linear-1.01-.013-.009-1.011	2	4
linear-1.013-.008-.011-1.008	4	6
flip	0	0
FMLR	15	10